

INTRODUCTION

This guide aims to lead communities through a process that can reveal and foster capacity for planning your own energy futures. Community visioning can be part of a collaborative approach to transforming your energy systems, one that recognises and builds on your community's existing knowledge. This guide can support you in designing and running visioning workshops that fit your community. It also offers opportunities to reflect on the role visioning can play in your energy planning.

About this guide

This guide was developed by the Clean Energy stream of SHARED GREEN DEAL, an EU Horizon 2020 project to stimulate shared actions on the European Green Deal (2022–2027). Academics, local authorities, and non-governmental organisations came together to design and undertake co-creative community visioning for clean energy futures in Bełchatów, Poland; Granada, Spain; and Jaywick, the United Kingdom. The guide was first developed in April 2023 for community visioning workshops held from May 2023 to April 2024.

Following these workshops, we updated the guide with lessons learned from this process, based on reflective interviews with the participants, facilitators, and organisers. In addition to guidelines, we have included quotes and case studies from this project to illustrate how community visioning can be implemented. For more information, visit www.sharedgreendeal.eu.

OUR CASES

Bełchatów, Poland
Polish Green Network

Photo: Alliance of Associations Polish Green Network, Piotr Chalubiński

Granada, Spain
Diputación de Granada

Photo: City of Granada

Jaywick, the United Kingdom
Essex County Council

Photo: Diamond Geezer via Flickr

WHAT IS COMMUNITY VISIONING?

Community visioning is an inclusive, collaborative process that enables a group of people to come together to imagine the future of their community – in this case, a clean energy future.

What does community visioning mean to you?

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF COMMUNITY VISIONING?

- Uncovering complex or unrecognised local energy challenges and possible solutions
- Building networks and strengthening community in a way that fosters trust and shared responsibility for community issues
- Inspiring big picture, creative thinking to address challenging problems that require more than simple solutions
- Bringing people with diverse perspectives together and breaking down existing power dynamics
- Demonstrating community support for certain solutions
- Revealing and addressing the social and justice issues that are part of the energy transition
- Strengthening the value of co-created, community knowledge in energy futures

How can visioning help your community?

"I believe that if we ever want to have real energy communities, it must start with these types of workshops where all the facets and parts of the energy issue are shared. Individually or within a single sector, we will not surely get there. Either we go together, or we don't get there."

- Community visioning participant from Granada

"[T]he best thing was perhaps having the opportunity to meet neighbours with whom I had been working for a long time in many meetings, but we hadn't had a relaxed space. To tell you the truth, also to talk about other topics besides the energy community, to get to know each other a little better... [W]e left the event recharged."

- Community visioning participant from Granada

Photo: Alliance of Associations Polish Green Network

"It was certainly successful... because it integrated participants and practically gave everyone the opportunity to voice themselves."

- Community visioning participant from Bełchatów

PRINCIPLES FOR CO-CREATIVE COMMUNITY VISIONING

- 1. All types of knowledge**, not just knowledge that comes from people we usually think of as experts, can make an equally valuable contribution to our understanding of energy systems. Indeed, solutions have often not worked in the past because they were missing a perspective, and community visioning aims to uncover ideas from multiple perspectives.
- 2.** Community visioning is **co-creative**, meaning that all participants (including the workshop organisers and facilitators) work together to develop the visions.
- 3.** There is **no 'right answer'** in this process, and consensus on a single vision is not required. The aim is to spark creativity and learning about energy and the role it plays in our lives, support community ownership over energy issues, and facilitate participation in shaping a community's future.
- 4.** There is no one way to do community visioning. Various and multiple methods can be used to imagine the future. The process in this guide centres around a series of **co-creative workshops**, which can take many different forms, including group discussions, creative arts, and interactive exercises.
- 5.** Community visioning is an **ongoing, iterative process** where we are continually reviewing, refining and improving.

What principles would you add?

OVERVIEW OF THE VISIONING MODEL

The overall community visioning structure suggested in this guide can be adapted to fit your community's needs – for example, you may wish to adjust the overall timeline, timing, general structure, or progression of the workshops.

Overall timeframe

- 1 year

Structure

- 4 workshops total: 3 stakeholder workshops (policy, business, residents) followed by 1 joint workshop (all stakeholder groups)
- 3-hour duration per workshop
- Approximately 20 participants at each event

What structure would best suit your community?

"...I think it's great that everyone's in a room hearing the same thing, and also making just new connections actually. It was great just to meet people and have those conversations with health colleagues that were there and for us all to realise that actually we are all in it together, most of us know that, but actually it's really helpful and a lot of these complex problems we can only move them forward by working together. I think by doing more of these sorts of workshop[s,] I think that is definitely the way to go."

- Community visioning participant from Jaywick

TIP

Holding separate meetings for different stakeholder groups can offer each group a safe space to share their experiences and perspectives and gain confidence before meeting with other groups. Consider the order of the stakeholder workshops. For example, would it make sense to meet first with the policy group, or with the residents? How could this affect the process? The final joint event can build the basis for future collaboration.

PHASE 1 - PLANNING

Prepare for your community visioning workshops with a clear plan that will help you stay organised. You can change and update your plan in response to the dynamic situation in your community and what happens at the workshops. Here are some guidelines you might want to consider in the planning process.

1. Form a **team** that will be responsible for designing and organising the visioning process. Typically, a team of 3 to 5 people works best (less than 3 people may be too onerous, but more than 5 people may be too difficult to manage).
 - The workshops should be organised and led by trusted actors to lend credibility to the process. Engaging an external facilitator, a skilled person with the buy-in of active community members, can allow organisers the time and space to get involved as participants.
 - Consider the best format: do you have a strong team with all the necessary skills? Do you need to form partnerships with other institutions or groups? Should you select a board to oversee the work?
 - Clarify what role everyone will play and enforce the need for a collaborative, equitable partnership.
 - Ensure that your team has, is willing to learn, or can identify a partner with the skills needed to carry out the visioning (e.g. facilitation, writing, communication, graphic design, project management). Establish any training needs.
 - Create a shared filing system. Ensure that information that should remain confidential, such as personal information related to workshop attendants, can be stored securely.

TIP

Design community visioning with input from the people you want to take part in it. Not only does getting them involved from the beginning keep them invested in the process, but it also helps connect visioning with the reality of the community. Openly discuss expectations, values, approaches, capacities, and goals to establish clear cooperation. Allow a lot of time for building relationships with stakeholders, as this is one of the most important parts of visioning and its long-term impact.

2. Align the team's **strategic objectives**, such as:

- Establishing strategic goals
 - Consider: why do you want to create a community vision? What does success look like? What outcomes or outputs will the process have? How do you plan to use them? How does this project align with your wider ethos? How do you want participants to feel when they finish the workshop?
 - Discuss the current energy systems and usage for the region.
 - Identify the current energy challenges, e.g. areas of high energy demand and costs of imported energy.
 - Understand the existing political situation in the community and consider how to best frame your initiative and which stakeholders are required for its success. You might need to adjust the scope of community visioning, plans for carrying it out, or the very goals of the process as it progresses.
 - Set a vision timeframe, e.g. 2050.
- Uncover internal expectations for the experiment.
 - Discuss past experiences of community engagement. How will this build or improve upon them? Are there any lessons that you have learned that you can bring to this experiment?
 - Agree on the principles and approaches you will uphold in the process.
- Create a project timeline with key dates and deadlines (being mindful of the most convenient times for potential participants, as well as local holidays).

3. Prepare a **Community Engagement Plan**, which should include a detailed community profile focusing on the following groups:

- Representatives from government, policy-makers (regional, local, etc.);
- Representatives from local businesses and relevant national or international businesses, both public and private, including renewable energy technology professionals; and
- Representatives from the community in the area (i.e. residents).

Identify who to target within each group, the various recruitment methods you will use (such as social media platforms, communal post boards, local radio or television or local newspapers) and ways to encourage these groups to see the value in the community visioning and take ownership of it.

4. Find a **venue** that will be suitable for the visioning workshops, check availability, and reserve it in advance.

- Will the chosen venue be a comfortable environment for participants to engage in community visioning? Although there is unlikely to be a perfect location, certain factors can make participants more willing to attend and make the workshops more enjoyable.
- Is the venue easily accessible, facilitated with public transport options, and does it have sufficient parking? Is the location and building accessible for those in wheelchairs or with other mobility issues? Does the venue have enough space or the right type of space for the activities you would like to do? What is the history of the space or its role within the community? Is it a space where everyone can feel comfortable and free to share their opinions? How can you make it a welcoming environment? Can refreshments be supplied?
- Consider what tools and stationery will be required (e.g. projector, audio/visual recording, white boards, flipcharts, sticky notes, pens/markers) and whether the space has these available or can accommodate them.
- Consider what accommodations related to work or home obligations you can make when planning the workshops to help community members participate, such as the timing of the workshops, childcare provisions, etc.

5. Develop a **communication plan** for both internal and external communication. Decide what modes of communication will be used, e.g. email, messaging applications, social media platforms.

TIP

Be ready to be flexible: although careful planning is crucial, unexpected developments can arise at any stage. Changing your plans along the way can help adapt your project to these developments and ensure community visioning remains meaningful.

CASE STUDY

Granada: community visions for community energy

The provincial authority in Granada, the Diputación de Granada, carried out community visioning across the province with the goal of promoting energy communities. They worked with four local organisations specialising in various aspects of energy communities, such as social engagement, technical installation, or economics, to develop 13 workshops that would help people with varying forms of participation in the energy transition, from rural residents to energy community members, imagine a distributed, renewable, efficient energy future.

Their goal was to reach rural residents across a wider territory. Some workshops were held with rural municipalities to discuss their visions for clean energy and answer their questions about how to implement them; others were with rural residents to envision a more efficient energy future. A few workshops were held to build capacity within existing energy communities through futures thinking, and others were large events for professionals and residents to discuss different aspects of the future of energy, such as legal frameworks, energy colonialism, and the role of shared visions.

Photo: Diputación de Granada

Following community visioning, the Diputación took the lessons learned from the workshops and put them to use in a new energy community support office, funded by the national government, which offers advice to those seeking to start energy community initiatives throughout the province.

PHASE 2 - RECRUITING PARTICIPANTS

With the in-depth preparations in Phase 1 complete, you will have a good understanding of the community profile so that your recruitment can equitably target all groups (government, businesses and residents).

Recruiting diverse participants

Recruiting your community for the visioning workshops does not require you to get a representative sample of the community in a strict sense. That being said, the benefits of bringing diverse perspectives together can help generate a wide, varied and rich sense of the challenges the community faces and some novel solutions.

Getting all these different kinds of people to your workshops might be challenging. So, consider carefully why community members

would give up their time to participate and how you can reach them in an effective way. What is the importance of the project to the community? And how can you get that message across in your recruitment? How do you build trusting relationships and how do you generate community ownership? What forms of compensation might be appropriate, or how can you make it a pleasant experience that people feel welcome and excited to join?

"With representatives from different groups, from different levels, and different spheres, this information, after being worked out at the meeting, has the possibility of reaching a wider part of society. If there are representatives of only one social group, for example, just the residents, typical working people, even if they run their own businesses, I think it will be difficult for them to come up with any ideas and implement any changes if, for example, they do not have representatives of non-governmental organisations who know how to act for the community."

- Community visioning participant from Bełchatów

TIP

Bring people with a diverse range of knowledge and skills together and find ways for them to meet each other and work together. As people tend to stick with those they already know at workshops, take intentional steps to ensure that participants can mingle, form new networks, and learn from others' experiences. Bringing these groups together helps to ensure that everyone is in the same room hearing the same thing, building the basis for moving forward together.

- Implement your Community Engagement Plan. Communications should include clear instructions on how community members can register their interest in taking part in the project.
- You can send invitations to interested and/or targeted community members and organisations. Include clear instructions on how to register for the workshop so you know how many participants to expect.
- You can also send or post an open invitation (where anyone is welcome to join). Use many formats and channels and circulate the invitation widely. Use modes of communication that your target group uses and go to the places they go to (virtual or physical) to get in contact with them.
- Consider whether there are any appropriate and available ways to compensate participants for their participation.

"[W]hen it comes to attracting the audience to participant in such events and such projects, I would also recommend doing some initial reach out [to] different groups to ask them, 'Do you find [this] interesting or what would make you [a] participant in this project?'"

- Community visioning organiser from Bełchatów

TIP

Communicate with participants regularly and clearly. Think carefully about what messages to use to attract and keep participants. Consider: why would they attend, what will they get out of it, what approach will be used, what time commitment is required, and what are the organisers' motivations and goals? Think carefully about and test the language you should use to communicate this so that it builds trust.

"Allow lots of time for building relationships with stakeholders, particularly in the community – and then add some more. These relationships are absolutely key to the success of this kind of initiative... Take time to think through the language of the project, the invitation to participants and to reflect on unintended consequences, so these can be mitigated through the project design."

- Community visioning organiser from Jaywick

PHASE 3 - DEVELOPING VISIONS: THE WORKSHOPS

Step 1 - Prepare for the stakeholder visioning workshops

- Select a suitable time and venue.
- Prepare the agenda.
- Pre-order food and refreshments, e.g. tea/coffee on arrival, water, lunch.
- Resource the required equipment (e.g. projector, whiteboard, flipcharts, sticky notes, paper, pens, audio-visual recording materials or notetaking materials).
- Supply childcare, if necessary.
- Prepare materials such as a sign-in sheet to record participant names and contact details; consent forms; and any documents your participants will be working with during the workshops.
- Consider rehearsing or doing a run-through of the workshop in the space.

How to craft an agenda

Every community's visioning workshops can look different, depending on the topics you want to address and the ways you want to engage your community. The goal of visioning is to generate imagined energy futures, but not necessarily to agree on the single 'right' future for the community. Remember that the key principle behind the workshops is co-creation: how can you bring people together to collaborate?

Keeping the agenda and the activities simple can help maximise the short amount of time you have to get deep conversations going.

Photo: Essex County Council

Consider some of the following elements for your workshop:

1. Creating a welcoming atmosphere
2. Icebreakers – these help people get to know each other
3. Presentation of the current situation in the community related to topics like energy, the environment, climate change, social issues, well-being – this can be done as a formal presentation or in a more creative format
 - o Find the right entry point for engaging people who may not work on ‘energy’ topics every day. This might mean translating ‘energy,’ for example, into how it works in people’s lives (i.e. ‘Energy powers the stove you use to cook and the mobile phone you use to communicate.’).
4. Reflection questions to elicit: how people feel in their community, what they value, what it means to be of or from that place, what energy practices they have, what they value about energy, and their concerns

“[T]he participatory or group dynamics [of] workshops... will start to create that spark, that dynamic of complicity or empathy. Because you see that this person more or less has interests like yours or simply sometimes by looking at a person you can communicate a lot.”

- Community visioning participant from Granada

TIP

Adapt the language used to talk about energy and the future for the specific participant group you are working with. This will help include them and give them confidence on the topic. Energy itself might not even emerge as a key topic – yet this can reveal what aspects of energy (e.g. social or relationship factors) are most important to people.

“Build a trustful environment so everybody can be relaxed and tell their opinions, their needs or what they really think... [O]nce you have the people there, start to speak about this topic you are interested in in a relaxed way and going further and further depending on how do you see then the people is reacting... [S]peaking about very serious issues, it’s nice when you really identify the people that is really wanting to do something and want to go for the next step, but in the zero phase... it is nice that you use as well gamification or other kind of storytelling, video-telling, more fun methodologies, so you are going to be able to build this trust and relax the atmosphere to let the people really speak and think about it.”

- Community visioning organiser from Granada

5. A central question for visioning, such as:

- What does our community look like in 2050?
- What if our community produced its own energy in 2050? How does our community look? How would it feel to live there?
- What changes would you like to see in our community in the next 30 years?
- What is your vision for how energy is managed in our community in 30 years?
- What does our city without air pollution look like in 2050?
- What could we do in the next 2 months, 2 years, and 10 years if we all worked together on energy?

TIP

Discussing the present is key to discussing the future, and visioning is most impactful for some communities when it begins with and is rooted in an understanding of the current situation in a place. Setting different timescales for visioning (i.e. two months, two years, ten years) may help keep visioning connected to the concerns that people have about their current situations and make visioning feel more productive.

6. Creative methods such as visualisations, art, sticky notes, poster-making, or storytelling

7. Small group work so everyone gets a chance to contribute

8. Presentation and discussion of the visions, allowing groups to decide how they present their contributions

9. Sufficient break time

10. A closing that reflects on the day's activities and sets participants up for the final, joint workshop

Consider whether you can repeat the same agenda for each group, or whether you need tailored agendas for different workshops.

TIP

Use engaging, fun, and dynamic activities that are attractive to people or where they can learn a new skill. For participant groups that have little experience thinking about or discussing energy, such formats can be a way to start engaging them on this serious topic.

"It can't be a simple discussion, where we invite people to chat, because it's tiring, boring and people don't want to listen to it. With storytelling, for example, people don't know what's up, there's that curiosity factor: 'I'll go and see what it's all about'. It acted as a magnet that attracted participants... Discussing transition wasn't the hook, but the fact that there was some storytelling or comedy."

- Community visioning participant from Bełchatów

CASE STUDY

The future starts now: design the tomorrow of Bełchatów

Bełchatów is home to the largest coal plant in Europe as well as a lignite mine, and it is therefore one of the EU's "just transition" regions, which will receive financing to ensure that the closure of the coal industry and transition to a more sustainable economy is done fairly. However, public consultation on this process has largely excluded women, as men are the primary employees of the coal plant.

This experiment sought to engage women residents in imagining a future after coal through creative activities such as improvisational theatre and storytelling, as well as an interactive discussion workshop with local women leaders and a panel discussion with women experts on the just transition in Poland. Women not only learned about the transition and gained new skills, but they formed lasting relationships. This experience was influential in convincing local authorities to set aside the maximum amount of European Union funding available for non-governmental organisations and women to be involved in planning and implementing the transition.

Photo: Alliance of Associations Polish Green Network

Photo: Diputación de Granada

TIP

Include refreshments or a meal in your workshops. This can not only help to attract some participants, but it also offers an opportunity for participants to build relationships and make connections on a more personal level.

Step 2 - Community Visioning Workshop Practicalities

Here are some guidelines for running the workshops:

- Open and prepare the venue early with tea/coffee ready for participant arrival.
- Set-up the venue, arrange tables and chairs, and set out materials participants will need.
- Set up a registration table with the participant sign-in sheet and consent forms (as needed).
- Follow the agenda you have set.
- Give everyone on the team clear responsibilities, including facilitation, timekeeping, and notetaking.
- Give participants clear instructions for the key details of the location and how the day will run, such as how long the event will be, where the toilets are located, etc. This can help participants focus on the task.
- Record all the ideas generated, take photos of flipcharts and collect completed participant materials.

"While experimenting is important, some elements must be designed with care, such as logistics and technical aspects of event preparation. These elements are universal, so make sure you have a checklist and follow it, especially if multiple events are planned."

- Community visioning organiser from Bełchatów

TIP

A relaxed, casual, and comfortable environment where people feel free to say what they think is conducive to community visioning. Organisers can help create this by offering multiple small, casual events as opposed to big, formal events; building in opportunities for small group work; considering anonymous or informal ways to give input; and preparing participants in advance for a casual event.

Facilitation guidelines

Facilitators encourage and guide activities rather than lecture, direct, or lead them. They try to start conversation and allow everyone to participate. Good facilitators encourage participants, listen actively, and intervene when necessary to move things along.

Here are some guidelines for the facilitation team:

- Be prepared for the sessions and make sure there is a clear agenda everyone is aware of.
- State expectations, objectives, and instructions clearly – make sure these are planned in advance.
- Talk the way people talk – stay away from academic, formal, or policy language if the workshop participants aren't familiar with it.
- Be aware of participants' multiple styles of intelligence and ways of engaging.
- Bring people together on an equal playing field.
- Allow people who have not contributed to the discussion an opportunity to add, without singling out one person.
- Food and drink are equalisers – consider where they are placed, when they are served, and how they are served to ensure this equalising effect.
- Arrange seating in a way that reduces power imbalances;
- Stay on time for each task and keep the group focused if they start to veer from the objectives of a session.

TIP

Give participants ownership over community visioning. This can be done in different ways; for example, you might wish to let participants facilitate small group work or identify the topics they want to discuss.

Photo: Essex County Council

Step 3 - Compile Outputs

- Take detailed notes in case digital records get lost or corrupted.
- Transfer the record of ideas generated (photos, video, audio, notes) to computer files.
- Consider synthesising the visions within and between each group into visual or narrative formats.

TIP

Build in opportunities for participants to reflect on community visioning and to share these reflections with the organisers. This feedback can help direct the process further, as well as help participants consolidate their own learning and experiences.

Step 4 - Joint Community Sector Workshop

Invite representatives from all four visioning workshops to a combined meeting to present a synthesis of the four previous visioning workshop outcomes and scenarios.

The joint workshop can be designed in a way that best fits your outputs from the first three workshops and your desired outcomes for the process. You might:

- Mix up the participants in terms of where they sit and who they work with, so that participants can exchange ideas with those from different sectors.
- Present and discuss the visions or outcomes from each workshop.
- Encourage reflection and deliberation on the various visions and outcomes, including, barriers and enablers.
- Refine the visions based on the joint community sector workshop.

Record the discussions and their outcomes via photo, video, audio, and/or written notetaking.

"I found it really beneficial finding out what other people are doing. We just hear what we're doing but it was really useful hearing what Essex County Council or even local residents [were doing] ... like I wasn't aware... there was a local group that are actually pushing for energy efficiency and so on. Yeah, I'd say the more interacting between different people, the better really."

- Community visioning participant from Jaywick

TIP

Consider success widely. A single vision emerging from the workshops is not necessarily the only indicator that community visioning has been a meaningful process; in some cases, just getting people to think about energy can be a success. In other cases, developing a wide diversity of visions might be the outcome.

PHASE 4 - TAKING YOUR COMMUNITY VISIONS FORWARD

Based on the visions and the many things you have learned in creating them, what actions can you and other community members take? Build on the engagement and energy generated throughout the visioning, as well as the connections made with the very people who can help carry out different parts of the vision. Be open to the visioning outcomes taking many forms and developing the path forward as you go.

The most important step in this phase is to follow up with the workshop participants and your partners. You can explain what happened, what the outcomes were, and what the outcomes will be used for. No commitments need to be made, but everyone who was involved in the project should be able to see what the impact of the community visioning process has been. This feedback can take many forms: a video, a newspaper article, an email, etc.

You may wish to consider how to create a lasting social group, network, community through the events, perhaps providing space for people to exchange contact information or facilitating a platform to remain connected. You may also wish to share your process and outcomes with others who might be interested in doing something similar and could learn from your experience.

TIP

Follow up with action. This starts with thinking early on and frequently throughout the process about what might result, what organisers can offer, what different actors can do if they work together, and grounding community visioning in action. Helping participants see they have the power to be part of this follow-up is one way to build confidence and make the experience meaningful. If you don't have funding to follow up on the visioning, can you think of actions that cost little but mean a lot, ways to draw on existing funding, or how to leverage the process to apply for more funding?

"[T]his is an acute problem that is urgent, we need to get cracking. And you could take three years to do the perfect thing, but what's the point? If you can do something good in a year, get it done, move on... make some stuff happen. Don't spend too long talking about it! ... [I]t's that tension, isn't it, of how much is enough, what's good enough to make a difference without holding out for it to be perfect?"

- Community visioning organiser from Jaywick

CASE STUDY

Jaywick's stories of change: improving energy and health futures

Led by Essex County Council, community visioning in Jaywick brought policy actors, the energy sector, and residents together to discuss what they could do if they all worked together on energy. In this coastal area facing high levels of deprivation and challenges keeping their homes warm and healthy, as well as a history of mistrust with energy companies and installers, household energy use and efficiency was high on the agenda.

With extensive outreach and relationship building, Essex County Council developed messaging to reach out to the various stakeholders that could make a difference in Essex, taking energy in a holistic view. They also sought to embed the visioning in existing programmes and use it to link different actors to existing sources of funding that could support energy efficiency in Jaywick. They held one workshop with local and regional public sector actors, one workshop with the energy sector and businesses (focused on private sector energy professionals), and one workshop with residents. They followed this with a joint workshop that brought all groups together.

Through the process, Essex County Council learned that residents were enthusiastic and willing to do more to improve their energy situations, with the support of trusted actors such as the Council. Community visioning led to the idea of an energy hub to offer peer advice, but also to help residents apply for benefits. This hub was launched in 2024; two community energy champions offer advice to other residents and have helped them apply for hundreds of thousands of pounds in unclaimed benefits.

Photo: Essex County Council

WORKBOOK

COMMUNITY VISIONING

WORKSHOP PLAN

This workbook can be used for planning community visioning workshops. Adjust the template so that it fits your needs. Throughout the process, you can return to the plan and note how things went or make changes if needed.

Location	
Authors of the plan	
Date of plan / version	
Goals <i>What are your objectives for community visioning?</i>	
Team and roles	

<p>Team communication methods <i>How will you communicate between the team and how will you store and share files?</i></p>	
<p>Community context <i>What challenge or issue do you plan to address?</i></p>	
<p>Timeline <i>Detail a timeline for your community visioning process.</i></p>	
<p>Community engagement plan <i>Who will you engage? How will you engage them?</i></p>	
<p>Venue and logistics</p>	

<p>Workshop agenda <i>Prepare your workshop agenda in detail, including timing and potential scripts for the different sessions.</i></p>	
<p>Resources needed</p>	
<p>Joint workshop agenda <i>Prepare your workshop agenda in detail here, including timing and potential scripts for the different sessions.</i></p>	
<p>Resources needed</p>	
<p>Communication and outreach plan <i>Detail how you will communicate your process and outcomes with participants and the public.</i></p>	

Resources

This guide draws on the concept of community visioning originally proposed by Ames (2010) and explored in depth by several other authors, including Walzer and Hamm (2012). To draft this guide, we drew upon existing community visioning guides, academic papers, and our own experiences in participatory-action research and community engagement in energy.

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Acknowledgements

This guidebook is the product of a collaboration between the University of Galway, Anglia Ruskin University, CEE Bankwatch Network, Alliance of Associations Polish Green Network, Diputación de Granada, Essex County Council, and Fonden Motorfabrikken and Blue Innovators. I would like to acknowledge the following individuals for their valuable contributions: Kyle Buckle-Hodgson, Nuala Carr, Thomas Estrup, Frances Fahy, Christophe Jost, Mateusz Kowalik, Gonzalo Esteban López, Rachel McArdle, Alina Pogoda, Jana Pospíšilová, Melanie Rohse, Louise Tennekoon, and Manuel Ibáñez Vázquez.

The visual identity and graphics for SHARED GREEN DEAL, used in this guidebook, were designed by Acento Comunicación.

This guidebook was supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036640. Social sciences & Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable GREEN DEAL (SHARED GREEN DEAL) is a €5m EU investment, coordinated by Anglia Ruskin University (UK).

Cover photo: Community visioning in Jaywick, the United Kingdom. Photo by Essex County Council.

How to cite this guidebook

Gray, E. K., 2025. *Community Visioning: A Guide to Co-creating Clean Energy Futures*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17086736>.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036640.

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